

Social Media - Relationship of Crypto currency Blockchain and Social Media

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Social Media is being used to promote blockchain and cryptocurrency. Social media groups are big on influencing the markets, bring news and awareness to anyone in cryptocurrency. Also blockchain Cryptocurrency is effecting Social media as in new blockchain based social medias are being created.

2. Aim

To discuss the changes social media creates in blockchain and cryptocurrency. The ways blockchain has created new forms of social media. relationship between social media, cryptocurrency and blockchain continues to evolve in new and exciting ways

3. Material and Methods

Utilize various resources / articles on this matter of social media / News Stories etc
-use of blockchain based social

4. Results

Blockchain based social media networks can offer many things (mentioned in presentation)

Social media can influence market and teach people about cryptocurrency.

Blockchain creates new technology and new methods of social media

Shift of social media

5. Conclusions

Social media will change based on new tech in blockchain technology

Cryptocurrency, market is influenced more from social media

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Author biography

John R John of Exciting World Cryptos.
He has been involved in Cryptocurrency from 2017.
To Offer The Best Promotion and Support
For Anyone Involved in Cryptocurrency

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